

**The Dual Nature of Plea Bargaining: Efficacy vs. Coercion in the American Judicial
System**

Allison Knoedler

2025

Abstract

Plea bargaining dominates the American criminal justice system, resolving the vast majority of cases without trial. While often justified as a necessary mechanism for managing overwhelming caseloads, this reliance raises serious concerns about fairness, coercion, and the preservation of constitutional rights. This paper examines the dual nature of plea bargaining, exploring both its practical benefits—such as efficiency and predictability—and its ethical drawbacks, including the risk of coercing innocent defendants and disproportionately impacting vulnerable populations. Particular attention is given to the phenomenon known as the “trial tax,” in which defendants face significantly harsher penalties for exercising their right to trial. Drawing on legal scholarship, case law, and contemporary critiques, the analysis argues that plea bargaining, while indispensable to the functioning of the courts, often prioritizes expedience over justice. The paper concludes by advocating for reforms aimed at reducing coercive pressures and ensuring that plea agreements are entered voluntarily and with full awareness of their consequences.

Keywords: *plea bargaining, trial tax, coercion, criminal justice reform, due process, constitutional rights*

The Dual Nature of Plea Bargaining: Efficacy vs. Coercion in the American Judicial System

As Bibas, Brower, and Hessick (2020) so powerfully state, the overwhelming reliance on plea bargaining is a response to the unmanageable volume of criminal cases; this expedience often comes at the cost of fairness, due process, and an individual's constitutional rights. The American judicial system is built on principles of fairness, due process, and the right to a trial—but in reality, many defendants are left with little choice. Faced with the threat of harsher punishments if they go to trial—a phenomenon known as the "trial tax"—where a number of people accept plea deals, whether or not they are guilty. In many minds, the cost of exercising one's constitutional rights is too high and not worth the sentencing fee. Opting to go to trial often means risking significantly longer sentences; without regard to the strength of the evidence. This national reliance on plea bargaining reflects a system that is more concerned with efficiency than justice. While taking a plea deal may offer some practical advantages, they also raise serious ethical concerns. For many in the courtroom, the implications of plea bargaining are complex and often troubling. Plea deals come with pros and cons for the players of the courtroom that argue that both direct and systematic coercion is an undeniable reality for many who accept these pressure-packed deals.

Bargaining with Justice

A primary justification for a plea bargain is the ability to streamline an already overburdened system. For prosecutors, it helps ensure steady convictions without the time, cost, or the uncertainty of a trial. Judges typically benefit from reduced dockets with quicker case turnover. Defense attorneys also benefit by securing more lenient sentences for their clients, doing so through negotiation rather than litigation. For many facing these commonly life-altering

situations offer a way to avoid a possible harsher penalty, especially when there are bad facts and the evidence is strong. As Bibas et al. (2020) note, the overwhelming caseloads in today's justice system have made plea deals an essential part. In this context, plea deals may be seen as strategic compromises with potential benefits for all courtroom participants.

Despite any legal advantages, plea bargaining often comes with profound drawbacks, many of which compromise the ethics and principles of justice. Prosecutors (or the Commonwealth) may put pressure on defendants by stacking charges or overreaching. This creates a dynamic that favors compliance over innocence— a “yes, your Honor” over the truth. Many defense attorneys and public defenders are overworked and underpaid, which may allow plea bargains to sound more encouraging to take instead of heading to a trial. Unfortunately, judges are often short-sighted on whether a plea was fully and knowingly voluntary. The most concerning fact is the risk of the number of innocent people who take a guilty plea just to avoid a harsher sentence. Ravina (2025) strongly emphasizes that such “strategic guilt” illustrates how plea deals may distort justice, and particularly so for underrepresented defendants.

The Price of Innocence

“Trial tax”, as it has been coined, refers to the punitive consequences a person may face when they choose to assert their right to a trial, instead of quickly agreeing with the prosecuting party. This penalty can be significant, sometimes adding years or even decades to a person's sentence. Plea deals often have a coercive effect, particularly on poor and underrepresented individuals. Sabelli (2024) describes the trial tax as a stand-out feature of coercive pleas; where people are punished for exercising their right to a trial instead of being punished for the crime itself.

This raises a deeply troubling contradiction: the Constitution guarantees a person the right to a fair trial, but the system punishes people who try to use that right. Add in the fact that over 95 percent of criminal convictions in both federal and state courts result from plea deals speaks to the overwhelming power imbalance and practical coercion within the system (*Missouri v. Frye*, 2012). As a result, defendants, especially those without legal knowledge or resources, are cornered into deals that may not reflect the truth. The justice system in theory, is meant to exist to uncover the truth and deliver justice through fairness. Seeing the implementation of “trial tax”, its weight has created a prioritization of speed over justice.

Pleading for Reform

The current system with plea bargaining offers some benefits and possible dangers. While caseloads seemingly are better managed with easier resolution, it also undermines the foundational principle of fairness and truth. For those in a legal profession, a plea deal is commonly a tool of negotiation, but for the defendant, it may feel like coercion in disguise.

In order to restore balance within the criminal justice system, reforms are needed to reduce prosecutorial overreaching and ensure that plea deals are truly voluntary. Reforms are also a necessity to help lessen the massive disparity between plea offers and post-trial sentences. Until if or when that comes, plea bargains will remain a dual-edged sword—serving the system’s needs at the expense of a defendant’s rights.

References

- Bibas, S., Brower, G., & Hessick, C. B. (2020). The pros and cons of plea bargaining. *University of Dayton Law Review*, 45 (4), 637–648.
https://scholarship.law.upenn.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1352&context=faculty_articles
- Missouri v. Frye, 566 U.S. 134 (2012).
- Ravina, S. (2025). *Defending David Cannon; unpacking the unfairness of plea bargains through bargaining theory* [Master's thesis, Emory University]. Emory Theses and Dissertations.
<https://etd.library.emory.edu/concern/etds/h989r477f?locale=de>
- Sabelli, M. (2024). The trial penalty: Coercive plea bargaining. In M. Tonry (Ed.), *Excessive punishment: How the justice system creates mass incarceration* (pp. 161–186). Columbia University Press. <https://doi.org/10.7312/eise21216-009>
- Trivedi, S. (2020, September 30). Coercive plea bargaining has poisoned the criminal justice system. It's time to suck the venom out. | ACLU. *American Civil Liberties Union*.
<https://www.aclu.org/news/criminal-law-reform/coercive-plea-bargaining-has-poisoned-the-criminal-justice-system-its-time-to-suck-the-venom-out>

Author's Note

Allison Knoedler is an undergraduate researcher pursuing a degree in criminal justice with the goal of attending law school and becoming a criminal defense attorney. Her academic interests include constitutional rights, criminal procedure, and systemic issues affecting fairness in the justice system. This paper was completed on December 28, 2025, as part of her independent research on plea bargaining practices in the United States. Knoedler has conducted extensive observation of criminal court proceedings and case analysis to better understand the practical realities of plea negotiations and trial decision-making. She hopes to contribute to ongoing discussions about justice reform and the protection of defendants' rights.